

University of Novi Sad
**INSTITUTE
OF FOOD
TECHNOLOGY
IN NOVI SAD**

feed
congress

16-18 October, 2024
Novi Sad, Serbia

5th

**INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS
FOOD TECHNOLOGY,
QUALITY AND SAFETY**

e-ABSTRACT BOOK

ISBN 978-86-7994-063-6

V INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS “FOOD TECHNOLOGY, QUALITY AND SAFETY”, 16-18 OCTOBER 2024, NOVI SAD, REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Publisher

University of Novi Sad
Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad
Bulevar cara Lazara 1
21000 Novi Sad
Republic of Serbia

Main editor

Dr Ljubiša Šarić

Editor

Dr Renata Kovač
Dr Nataša Ćurčić
Dr Bojana Šarić

Abstract Review

All abstracts are peer-reviewed and supervised by the International Scientific Committee

Technical editor

Dragana Tomanić
Milica Vidosavljević

Cover

Boris Bartula, BIS, Novi Sad, Serbia

Organization of Congress:

- INSTITUTE OF FOOD TECHNOLOGY IN NOVI SAD, University of Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Co-Organizers of Congress:

- SHANDONG AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY, People's Republic of China
- INSTITUTE OF MEAT HYGIENE AND TECHNOLOGY, University of Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

Congress is supported by:

- Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia
- Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
- Provincial Secretariat for Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
- Provincial Secretariat for Regional Development, Interregional Cooperation and Local Self-Government, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
- Food and Feed Research, Journal of the Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Congress President:

Ljubiša Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

General sponsor: Analysis d.o.o. – Novi Beograd, Republic of Serbia

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

President:

Tamara Dapčević Hadnađev, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Members:

Aleksandar Marić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Aleksandra Jovanović Galović, Faculty of Pharmacy Novi Sad, University Business Academy, Serbia

Aleksandra Mišan, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Aleksandra Nikolić, Faculty of Agriculture and Food Science, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Aleksandra Novaković, Faculty of Education in Bijeljina, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Alexandrina Sirbu, FMMAE Râmnicu Vâlcea, Constantin Brâncoveanu University of Pitesti, Romania

Alena Stupar, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Anamarija Mandić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Anita Klaus, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Antonio Moretti, Institute of Sciences of Food Production, National Council of Research CNR-ISPA, Italy

Biljana Pajin, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Biljana Stojanovska Dimzoska, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Bojan Butinar, Institute for Olive culture, Science and Research Centre Koper, ZRS Koper, Slovenia

Bojana Kokić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Bojana Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Branislav Šojić, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Breda Jakovac Strajn, Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

Brijesh Tiwari, Teagasc - Agriculture and Food Development Authority, Ireland

Cristina M. Rosell, Department of Food and Human Nutritional Sciences, University of Manitoba, Canada

Dapeng Li, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China

Dejan Dragan Miladinović, Center for Feed Technology, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway

Diego A. Moreno-Fernández, CEBAS-CSIC, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Spain

Dragomir Catalin, National Institute for Research and Development in Animal Biology and Nutrition, Romania

Dragan Milić, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dragana Plavšić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dragana Ubiparip Samek, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dubravka Škrobot, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Elena Velickova Nikova, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Fatih Ozogul, Faculty of Fisheries, Cukurova University, Turkey

Feng Li, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China

Fatjon Hoxha, Agricultural University of Tirana, Albania
Filip Kulić, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Francesco Marra, Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno, Italy
Francisco Barba, University of Valencia, Spain
Giuseppina Avantaggiato, Institute of Sciences of Food Production, Bari, Italy
Gordana Dragović Lukić, Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Gul Ebru Orhun, Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Turkey
Hanxue Hou, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Igor Tomašević, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Ilias Giannenas, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Greece
Ines Banjari, Faculty of Food Technology Osijek, University of Osijek, Croatia
Ioannis Mourtzinou, School of Agriculture, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece
Ivan Pavkov, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ivana Čabarkapa, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ivana Živković, Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Serbia
Jana Klopčevska, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
Jasmina Lazarević, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelena Miljanić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelena Tomić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelka Pleadin, Croatian Veterinary Institute, Croatia
Josip Lepes, Gal Ferenc University, Hungary
Jovana Kos, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Kojić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Vunduk, Institute of General and Physical Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Jurislav Babić, Faculty of Food Technology Osijek, University of Osijek, Croatia
Katarina Šavikin, Institute for Medicinal Plants Research "Dr. Josif Pančić, Serbia
Katerina Dodovska Blagoevska, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine – Skopje, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
Kaye Burgess, Teagasc - Agriculture and Food Development Authority, Ireland
Krzysztof Klinecicz, Faculty of Management, University of Warsaw, Poland
Ljubiša Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Louise Dye, Institute for Sustainable Food, University of Sheffield, UK
Luciano Pinotti, Department of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Science (DIVAS), University of Milan, Italy
Maja Matoša Kočar, Agricultural Institute Osijek, University of Osijek, Croatia
Maja Rapajić, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Marcela Šperanda, Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences in Osijek, Josip Juraj Strossmayera University of Osijek, Croatia
Marco Garcia-Vaquero, UCD School of Agriculture and Food Science, University College Dublin, Ireland
Marija Milašinović Šeremešić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Marijana Sakač, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Matteo Ottoboni, Department of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Science (DIVAS), University of Milan, Italy

Mia Eeckhout, Department of Food Technology, Safety and Health, Ghent University, Belgium
Mian N. Riaz, Dept. of Food Science and Technology, Texas A&M University, USA
Mihaela Jurdana, Institute for Kinesiology Research, Science and Research Centre Koper, ZRS Koper, Slovenia
Milan Ilić, Faculty of Pharmacy Novi Sad, University Business Academy, Serbia
Milan Vraneš, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Milena Stranska, Faculty of Food and Biochemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Czech Republic
Milica Pojić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Milivoj Radojčin, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miloš Pelić, Scientific Veterinary Institute Novi Sad, Serbia
Miona Belović, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miroљjub Barać, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Miroslav Hadnađev, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Mladen Brnčić, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Mladenka Pestorić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nataša Ćurčić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nataša Jovanović Lješković, Faculty of Pharmacy Novi Sad, University Business Academy, Serbia
Nebojša Ilić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nemanja Teslić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nikola Tomić, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Nikolina Ćukelj Mustač, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Olivera Đuragić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Omer Said Toker, Chemical and Metallurgical Engineering Faculty, Food Engineering Department, Yildiz Technical University Istanbul, Turkey
Patrik Drid, Faculty of Sport and Physical Education, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Pavle Jovanov, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Pedro Silva, Instituto de Medicina Molecular, University of Lisbon, Portugal
Peter Raspor, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
Predrag Ikonić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Qingguo Wang, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Rada Jevtić Mučibabić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Relja Suručić, Faculty of Medicine, University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Renata Kovač, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ružica Tomičić, Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Sandra Zavadlav, Department of Food Technology, Karlovac University of Applied Sciences, Croatia
Sanja Belić, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Saša Despotović, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Slađana Rakita, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Slobodan Gadžurić, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Spiros Paramithiotis, Department of Biological Applications and Technologies, University of Ioannina, Greece
Szabo Balazs, Cereal Research Nonprofit Ltd., Hungary
Szabolcs Halazsi, Faculty of Pedagogy, Gal Ferenc University, Hungary

Tatjana Peulić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Verica Dragović-Uzelac, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, Croatia
Vesna Đorđević, Institute of Meat Hygiene and Technology, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Viktor Nedović, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Wei Chen, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Xiaoyong Sun, College of Information Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Xuguang Qiao, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Yilun Chen, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Yimin Zhang, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Žarko Kevrešan, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Zhixiang Xu, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Zlata Kralik, Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia
Zorica Stojanović, Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Zorica Tomičić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Zsuzsanna Jakabné Sándor, Research Centre for Aquaculture and Fisheries (HAKI), Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Hungary

EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE

Bojana Kokić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Bojana Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Kos, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ljubiša Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Pavle Jovanov, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Predrag Ikonić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Tamara Dapčević Hadnađev, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

President:

Pavle Jovanov, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Members:

Aleksandar Marić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Aleksandra Bajić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Alena Stupar, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Biljana Cvetković, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Bojana Radić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

663/664:658.562(048.3)
614.31(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety" (5 ; 2024 ; Novi Sad)

e-Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / 5th International Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety", 16-18 October 2024, Novi Sad ; [main editor Ljubiša Šarić]. - Novi Sad : Institute of Food Technology, 2024

Način pristupa (URL): https://fins.uns.ac.rs/publications/?_sft_publicationss=zbornik. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan 22.10.2024.

ISBN 978-86-7994-063-6

а) Животне намирнице -- Контрола квалитета -- Апстракти б) Животне намирнице -- Хигијена -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155106313

CATEGORIZATION OF FOOD BASED ON VITAMIN K-CONTENT FOR PREVENTING ACENOCOUMAROL-FOOD INTERACTIONS

Pinter Damir*, Jelena Jovičić-Bata, Maja Milanović, Nataša Milošević

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3 Novi Sad

*Corresponding author:

E-mail address: 904009d23@mf.uns.ac.rs

Acenocoumarol prevents carboxylation of vitamin K-dependent clotting factors II, VII, IX and X, and thus interferes with coagulation. Since vitamin K is a competitive antagonist of acenocoumarol, foods rich in vitamin K reduces the therapeutic effect of the drug. A single vitamin K-rich meal does not have major negative consequences during a 24h-period nor does 50 mcg vitamin K daily have a statistically significant impact on the international normalized ratio (INR) or the levels of uncarboxylated vitamin K-dependent coagulation factors. However, there are case reports about clinically relevant vitamin K rich food interactions with INR and/or acenocoumarol levels especially among geriatric patients with comorbidities. The vague guidelines on the use of acenocoumarol among elderly with food and the consequent INR fluctuations make the therapy less efficient and lead to more adverse reactions. In this study a dietary plan recommendation for patients who are taking acenocoumarol were made. Data on the average content of vitamin K were obtained from the U.S. Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Service (<https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/>). FAO tables were used to convert the amount of vitamin K in foods to micrograms per 100 g and divided into 4 categories:

Category I: < 5mcg vit K/100g: cooked potatoes, canned tuna

Category II: 5-10mcg vit K/100g: fat-free milk

Category III: 10-40mcg vit K/100g: carrots

Category IV: >40mcg vit K/100g: broccoli, green leaf lettuce, green beans, spinach, pickled cucumber, asparagus etc.

Raising awareness on the vitamin K-content category of specific foods among acenocoumarol-prescribed patients might reduce the risks of INR oscillations and other serious adverse effects of the drug simply by providing more clarity on vitamin K content of foods to patients.

Key words: acenocoumarol, vitamin K, international normalized ratio